

SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF OPIOID CRISIS

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Abstract: The dramatic rise in the number of Americans suffering from the opioid crisis in the United States continues to have a catastrophic effect on families and communities. This study utilizes ordinary least squares regression and machine learning techniques to investigate the social determinants of the opioid crisis. This model will also integrate mental health risk into these determinants, thereby addressing gaps in previous studies. This study uses cross-sectional data from the NCDAS 2023 records, US Census Bureau indicators, and a mental health risk assessment in the United States. This study also applied ordinary least squares regression and machine learning models for better precision in determining the social determinants of the opioid crisis. Meanwhile, the inclusion of mental health risk as a social determinant suggests that an increase in mental health risk exacerbates the opioid crisis, whereas an increase in economic stability leads to a decrease in the opioid crisis in the 51 states under review. Therefore, there is a need to adopt a sustainable policy that will mitigate mental health risk and enhance economic stability to effectively address the opioid crisis. At the individual and community levels, it is necessary to improve the material and social environment for those at risk of, struggling with, or recovering from the opioid crisis. Interventions may include interventions across the continuum of care: prevention, harm reduction, treatment, and recovery.

Keywords: Opioid crisis, Social Determinants, OLS regression, Machine learning

Introduction

The United States is currently grappling with an ongoing pandemic of drug overdose. The crisis dynamics are rapidly changing. During the late 1990s, the number of overdoses associated with prescription opioids increased substantially. Death rates attributed to heroin overdoses experienced an upward trend starting in 2010. According to Scholl et al. (2019), there has been a substantial increase in lethal overdoses associated with synthetic opioids, such as illegally manufactured fentanyl, since 2013. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the incidence of opioid use disorder has demonstrated a very stable trend, as documented by the US Department of Health and Human Services (2018). Dowell et al. (2017) reported data indicating that the illegal manufacturing of fentanyl, an extremely powerful opioid, causes the increase in opioid overdose deaths.

In addition, the United States experienced a threefold surge in opioid overdose mortality rates from 1999 to 2017. Hedegaard et al. (2018) found that opioid overdose was the main cause of 70,237 drug overdose deaths in the

United States in 2017. Gradually, the opioid crisis in the United States has experienced a metamorphosis. Dasgupta et al. (2018) reported that during the early 1980s, people primarily used opioids to treat acute pain, leading to a significant number of drug-related deaths due to improper use for non-medical purposes. Over the course of a decade, there was an increase in the prescription of opioids for managing long-term pain, mostly driven by the belief that existing treatments were insufficient. By 2000, this trend had accelerated with the discontinuation of commonly prescribed nonopioid analgesics due to cardiovascular risks and concerns about acetaminophen poisoning. By approximately 2010, there had been a notable increase in the prevalence of concurrent use of opiate analgesics and heroin. In the second half of the 2010s, there was an increasing frequency of counterfeit medicines and street drugs containing potent chemicals, such as fentanyl and its analogs.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic gaining significant media attention, the opioid crisis in the United States was widely acknowledged as one of the most severe public health disasters of our era (Darolia & Heflin, 2023). The number of opioid overdose fatalities in the United States in 2019 was approximately 50,000, a figure approximately six times higher than the number of deaths recorded in 2000. The opioid-related mortality rate experienced a significant increase of over 40% in 2020 compared with the previous year, reaching approximately 69,000 deaths. The mortality rate increased by an additional 20% in 2021, approaching a total of 81,000 deaths. The COVID-19 epidemic certainly intensified increase in opioid overdoses, possibly due to overcrowded health care institutions and the resulting isolation. Moreover, the COVID-19 and opioid crises exerted pressure on the public health, social service, and educational sectors (Heflin, 2023). This research aims to enhance understanding of the impacts of the opioid crisis on different aspects of society and communities, such as education, family formation, child welfare, employment markets, housing stability, access to food, and public finance. Several of these subjects currently lack sufficient research.

Heflin (2023) highlighted the presence of methodological obstacles in this field while simultaneously emphasizing the importance of several significant observations. To begin with, opiate addiction is a significant health concern that affects a substantial number of people. It is critical that comprehensive policies consider individual needs as a whole. For instance, individuals afflicted with opioid use disorders may require provisions such as sustenance and shelter, thereby diminishing the effectiveness of treatment strategies. Opioid-related legislation should comprehensively address such requirements, notwithstanding the considerable care required for opioid-related health difficulties.

Furthermore, individuals with opioid use disorders hold important societal responsibilities as parents, employees, and members of families and communities. Opioid use has the capacity to profoundly impact families across multiple generations. Moreover, the use of opioids can have adverse impacts on our educational system, burden social services such as child welfare, heighten food poverty, and diminish productivity, resulting in financial expenses that exceed the direct consequences noticed at the local and state levels. This indicates the necessity for extensive and wide-ranging remedies.

Several studies (Birnbaum et al., 2006; Birnbaum et al., 2011; Rice et al., 2014) have examined the financial impacts of opioid use disorder and fatal opioid overdose. The current research has primarily focused on prescription opioids. For instance, Florence et al. (2016) calculated that the economic consequences of prescription opioid use disorder and fatal overdoses in 2013 reached a total of \$78.5 billion (Florence et al., 2016). This evaluation considered the elements of healthcare, criminal justice, and economic deterioration. In 2017, the president's Council of Economic Advisers (CEA) released a report criticizing the methodology of the study by

Florence et al. The report noted that the study did not adequately include the broader societal impacts of fatal overdoses. In order to assess these costs, CEA included the concept of "willingness to pay" for reductions in the risk of death, which is known as the value of a statistical life (VSL). The CEA conducted a comprehensive assessment of the value of opioid use disorder and opioid overdose, resulting in an estimated economic effect of \$500 billion for 2015. Adejumo's latest study (2024) on the socioeconomic ramifications of opioid addiction death in the United States did not address the mental health risk, leaving a void that requires further investigation. Thus, to address the limitations of previous research, this study integrates mental health and economic stability as additional social determinants of opioid use in the United States. This was achieved using OLS regression and machine learning models.

Literature Review

Between 2012 and 2015, the nationwide count of prescriptions of opioid analgesics for patients outside hospitals decreased by 13%, as reported by the FDA in 2017. Significant reductions were observed in other regions. Consequently, the mortality rate of overdose of prescribed opioids has not exhibited any decline. However, during the same period, the country experienced a 38% increase in the overdose fatality rate, as reported by the CDCP in 2017. The decline in prescription opioid overdose mortality does not coincide with the level of accessibility. The associations between the volume of administered drugs and overdose rates at the county level were not as strong as those observed at the national level (Kertesz, 2017; Dasgupta et al., 2006). Different researchers, including Dasgupta et al. (2013) and Alexandridis et al. (2017), have come up with different ideas to try to explain why death rates are different for people who use synthetic opioids, why changing autopsy procedures might have an effect, why time-delay effects occur, and why some treatments do not work. It is logical to establish a connection between structural factors, such as poverty, limited opportunities, unfavorable living and working conditions, and poor health. This article does not provide a comprehensive analysis of the fundamental factors contributing to overdose, addiction, and pain. The growing availability of opioids may partially contribute to the increase in overdose cases; however, solely focusing on opioid supply undermines the efficacy of therapies (McCaig, 1996; Cicero et al., 2017). The "reversal of fortunes" in life expectancy were swiftly nationalized. Initially observed by academics in Appalachia and the Southwest in 2000, this trend had spread outside these areas by 2015 (Masters et al., 2017; Case & Deaton, 2017). Socioeconomic factors, racial and ethnicity, metabolic and behavioral risk, and access to healthcare have significantly influenced the disparity in life expectancy between the healthiest and least healthy counties over the past two decades (Dwyer-Lindgren et al., 2016). These indicators, such as a substantial rise in income inequality over several decades and the occurrence of economic shocks resulting from deindustrialization and decreases in social safety nets, offer the most recent evidence of an enduring downward trend. The 2008 financial crisis, austerity programs, and other neoliberal policies have had detrimental effects on physical and mental health (Ruckert & Labonté, 2017).

The relationship between substance misuse and poverty is particularly pronounced in individuals who experience mental health challenges and live-in insecure conditions. Disadvantaged demographics who work in manufacturing and service occupations that involve significant physical risk, like military duty, receive substantial payment. Prolonged work-related injuries can lead to persistent pain that can trigger a cycle of debilitation and impoverishment. Although opioid analgesics can assist those who are unable to work in maintaining employment, it appears that manual laborers are more likely to use them for non-medical reasons (Rigg & Monnat, 2015). The

counties with the lowest social capital had the highest rates of overdose in a significant portion of the country (Zoorob & Salemi, 2017).

Socioeconomic marginalization leads to vulnerability and exclusion from social and economic opportunities. The aforementioned scenarios encompass a variety of factors that result in individuals marginalizing employment opportunities, resorting to illegal or unofficial methods of income generation (such as theft, drug trafficking, or street labor), facing insufficient financial resources, facing imprisonment or social isolation, having a low socioeconomic status, living in poverty, and encountering material insecurity (such as unstable housing or food insecurity). Drug-related fatalities have a higher prevalence rate among specific subpopulations of people who use drugs compared to others. The groups included in this study are the homeless (Fischer et al., 2004), recently released from prison (Green et al., 2012), eligible for US Medicaid (a measure of poverty), the Indigenous population (Jongbloed et al., 2014), and low-income households headed by Indigenous individuals (Ho, 2017; Lanier et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2012). However, these characteristics are not sufficient to completely encompass the various socioeconomic factors that impact the health and likelihood of overdose among individuals taking opioids. Some of the things that lead to this are not being able to find work (Richardson et al., 2015), engaging in illegal and unethical financial activities (Ti et al., 2014), mismanaging income assistance payments (Krebs et al., 2016; Otterstatter et al., 2016; Zlotorzynska et al., 2014), and not having enough money (Ompad et al., 2011).

However, the field of overdose research has not adequately addressed these issues (Brunner and Marmot, 2006). Brunner and Marmot (2006) proposed that these factors, together with direct material deprivation, impact health outcomes by affecting psychological and behavioral pathways. Brunner and Marmot (2006) contend that prolonged stress stemming from devaluation, social exclusion, and inequality can trigger stress responses, escalating interpersonal conflict, and negatively impacting health. This perpetuates the power dynamics that gave rise to these circumstances. Marginalization, characterized by limited access to resources and factors that lead to drug-related damage, such as income inequality and neighborhood overtly, inherently connects individuals to drug overdose and drug-related death. The allocation and administration of socioeconomic resources serve as mediating factors in this association (Krebs et al., 2016; Lanier et al., 2012; Otterstatter et al., 2016; Xiang et al., 2012; Zlotorzynska et al., 2014).

Prior research has extensively examined conventional machine learning methods (Miotto et al., 2017; Shickel et al., 2018). Che et al. (2017) used a deep learning-based approach to categorize opioid patients into opioid-dependent or long-term opioid users for opioid-related purposes. Ellis et al. (2019) employed machine learning classifiers to predict the probability of patients exhibiting substance dependence.

The emergence of the coronavirus has intensified the opioid epidemic in the United States. The number of deaths caused by drug overdose reached an unprecedented peak of 93,331 in 2020. According to Baumgartner and David (2020), the percentage of overdose deaths involving opioids increased significantly from 18% in 2015 to over 60% in 2020, primarily due to the use of synthetic opioids. The pandemic may have intensified the opioid crisis by worsening mental health conditions (Zhang, 2023). The pandemic has introduced several stress-inducing factors, including unemployment, reduced social connections, and fear of contracting COVID-19. These factors have had a detrimental effect on mental health and have posed additional challenges for individuals struggling with mental illness and substance use problems (Zhang, 2023).

Identifying the underlying reasons for these interactions is difficult because multiple factors converge. The links found between these diseases and overdose, on the other hand, demonstrate how different types of disadvantages, like cumulative and spatial life course disadvantages, work together to worsen opioid users' health. Adejumo (2024) concluded that an increase in economic growth can decrease the opioid addiction epidemic in the United States. However, his study failed to consider the mental health risks linked to socioeconomic determinants, creating a gap that this study must fill. Thus, to address the deficiencies identified in previous research, this study integrates mental health and economic stability as social determinants of opioid use in the United States. This is achieved using ordinary least squares regression and machine learning models.

Methodology

For this investigation, a cross-sectional dataset was acquired from the 2023 records of the National Center for Drug Abuse Statistics (NCDAS). Statistics on the Opioid Crisis [2023]: The social determinants of the opioid epidemic in the United States were examined through prescription opioid abuse (drugabusestatistics.org) in 51 states, US Census Bureau indicators, and mental health risk assessment in all states. The cross-sectional data in this study were analyzed using a quantitative research methodology that included machine learning techniques like artificial neural networks (ANN), OLS regression models, and descriptive statistics. The OLS regression specification, which is based on Adejumo's (2024) work, will look like the following:

$$Opioid_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1(POV)_i + \beta_2(UNEMP)_i + \beta_3(EDUA)_i + \beta_4(ECS)_i + \beta_5(Mental)_i + \mu_i \tag{1}$$

Opioid crisis (Opioid) is the dependent variable, whereas the independent variable includes unemployment (UNEMP), educational attainment (EDUA) for residents with a bachelor's degree or higher, economic stability (ECS) measured using with the GDP by states in the United States, and mental health risk in the 51 states under review. In addition, poverty, unemployment rate, educational attainment, economic stability, and mental health risk are the social determinants considered in this study. Here, *i* is the cross-section of the 51 American states, β_0 is the constant term, β_1 to β_5 are the coefficient estimates of the independent variables, and μ_i is the error term or residuals.

In the meantime, this study carried out diagnostic checks, such as the multicollinearity, autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity test, normality test of the model residuals, and model stability test, to determine the validity of the OLS regression model.

Artificial neural network (ANN)

The input variables, output variable (the opioid crisis), and two hidden layers are modeled using this extremely sophisticated machine learning technique. In addition, this is a deep learning strategy that was altered from the deep learning machine model strategy used in Che et al. (2017) and Ellis et al. (2019). In this case, predicting or identifying the opioid problem using an artificial neural network makes perfect sense. It is an improved alternative to regression analysis and a better tool for predictive analytics.

The independent variables, accompanying weights, and the intercept term for each neuron are combined in a linear fashion to construct the neural network equation. This is how the neural network equation appears:

$$Opioid = \Pi_0 + \Pi_1X_1 + \Pi_2X_2 + \Pi_3X_3 + \Pi_4X_4 + \Pi_5X_5..... \tag{2}$$

Here, opioid crisis is the outcome variable of the ANN model.

Π_1 to Π_5 are the weights or beta coefficients, and intercept is denoted with Π_0

The hidden layer pattern is H (1,1) to H (1,5), and X1 to X5 represent the independent variables or inputs, such as poverty, unemployment, educational attainment, economic stability as measured by GDP, and mental health risk.

Figure 1: Typical structure of the ANN model.

Table 1: Variable Measurements

Variables	Measurement	Sources
Opioid Crisis	Deaths per 100,000	Opioid Crisis Statistics [2023]: Prescription Opioid Abuse (drugabusestatistics.org)
Poverty	Percentage	Population in the United States: 2022 (census.gov)
Unemployment	Percentage	Unemployment Rates for States (bls.gov)
Educational attainment	Percentage	S1501: EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT-Census Bureau Table
Economic stability	Millions of US Dollars	Gross Domestic Product by State and Personal Income by State, 4th Quarter 2023 and Preliminary 2023 U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA)
Mental health	Mental health risk per 100,000 people in the state	County and State Data Map: Defining Mental Health Across

Source: Authors' computation

Results

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	OPIOID	POVERTY	UNEMPLOYMENT	EDUCATION	ECS	MENTAL
Mean	15.79608	12.59529	3.539216	34.79157	533556.0	43.60784
Median	15.10000	12.36000	3.400000	34.45000	309601.0	43.30000
Maximum	42.40000	19.58000	5.300000	63.05000	3862171.	79.40000
Minimum	3.400000	7.420000	2.000000	24.12000	43130.00	31.60000
Std. Dev.	9.996719	2.718346	0.826336	7.032941	692205.0	7.351649
Observations	51	51	51	51	51	51

Source: Authors' computation

Table 2 indicates that the average opioid crisis in the United States is approximately 16 deaths per 100,000, with a variability of approximately 10 deaths per 100,000 across the 51 states under study. The average poverty rate is approximately 13%, with a variability of approximately 3%. The average unemployment rate is approximately 4%, with a variability of approximately 1%. The average education attainment of residents with a bachelor's degree or higher is approximately 35%, with a variability of approximately 7%. The average economic stability, measured by GDP across the 51 states, was approximately US \$533,556 million. Finally, the average mental health risk across the 51 states is approximately 44 risks per 100,000 of the state population.

Table 3: OLS Regression model

OPIOID	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	VIF
C	-0.636568	15.89982	-0.040036	0.9682	NA
POVERTY	0.079945	0.549832	0.145400	0.8850	1.416277
UNEMPLOYMENT	3.560495	1.746846	2.038242	0.0474	1.320997
EDUCATION	0.524225	0.212245	2.469909	0.0174	1.412623
ECS	-4.33E-06	2.04E-06	-2.126771	0.0390	1.261216
MENTAL HEALTH	0.300452	0.187527	1.602185	0.0161	1.204964
R-squared	0.289738	Mean dependent var	15.79608		
Adjusted R-squared	0.210820	S.D. dependent var	9.996719		
F-statistic	3.671385	Durbin-Watson stat	2.228298		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.007172				

Source: Authors' computation

Table 3 reveals that social determinants such as unemployment, education attainment of residents with a bachelor's degree or higher, and mental health risk has a positive and significant impact on the opioid crisis in

the United States. Conversely, the coefficient estimates of economic stability have a negative significant influence on the opioid crisis. This suggests that an increase in unemployment, education attainment of residents with a bachelor’s degree or higher, and mental health risk will exacerbate the opioid crisis in the United States, whereas an increase in economic stability will alleviate it. The overall model probability value of 0.007 indicates that the fitted OLS regression is statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that the opioid crisis is significantly associated with social determinants such as poverty, unemployment, education attainment of residents with a bachelor’s degree or higher, economic stability, and mental health risk. The variance inflation factor (VIF) of all independent variables is less than 5. This means that the model does not suffer the multicollinearity problem. This means that the fitted OLS regression results are accurate and will not lead you astray. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 2.228 falls between the two critical values of 1.5 and 2.5, respectively, indicating that the fitted OLS regression model does not suffer from the issue of autocorrelation, satisfying the ordinary least squares (OLS) assumption.

Table 4: Heteroscedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.970675	Prob. F (5,45)	0.4459
Obs*R-squared	4.965004	Prob. Chi-Square (5)	0.4202
Scaled-explained SS	4.269150	Prob. Chi-Square (5)	0.5114

Source: Authors’ computation

Table 4 shows that the probability value of 0.4202 of the heteroscedasticity tests for the ordinary least squares (OLS) assumption test exceeds the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that the filled OLS regression model does not suffer from the heteroscedasticity problem and thus satisfies the OLS assumption.

Besides, Figure 2 shows the normality test results with a probability value of 0.06 that exceeds the 0.05 significance level, indicating that there is normality in the model residuals, satisfying the normality assumptions of the OLS, while Figure 3 demonstrates the CUSUM test, which indicates that the parameters of the fitted OLS regression model fall between the two 95% confidence intervals, suggesting that the OLS regression model is stable.

Figure 2: Test for normality of OLS regression Model Residuals

Figure 3: OLS regression CUSUM test of model stability

Table 5: Independent variable importance of ANN

	Importance	Normalized Importance
Poverty	0.114	37.0%
Unemployment	0.276	89.7%
Education	0.307	100.0%
ECS	0.231	75.2%
Mental health	0.072	23.5%

Model Summary

		N	Percentage
Sample	Training	36	70.6%
	Testing	15	29.4%
Valid		51	100.0%
Error Rate		0.001	

Source: Authors' computation

Table 5 presents the significance of the independent variables and their estimated contributions from the ANN model. It reveals that residents with a bachelor's degree or higher have the highest educational attainment, contributing 100% to the opioid crisis. This is followed by unemployment, economic stability, poverty, and mental health risk, each contributing 89.7%, 75.2%, 37%, and 23.5%, respectively. The estimated ANN demonstrated an accuracy of 70.6% with a minimal negligible error rate of 0.001, which outperformed the traditional OLS regression model's prediction of social determinants of opioid crises.

Figure 4 shows the normalized importance of the independent variables estimated by the ANN model, which demonstrates the contributions of each of the social determinants of the opioid crisis. Figure 5 shows the ANN structure with the input variable, hidden neuron, and output variable.

Figure 4: Chart of normalized independent variable importance of ANN

— Synaptic Weight > 0
 — Synaptic Weight < 0

Hidden layer activation function: Hyperbolic tangent
 Output layer activation function: Identity

Figure 5: Structure of estimated ANN model

Discussion

According to the study, the average opioid crisis in the United States is approximately 16 deaths per 100,000, with a variation of approximately 10 deaths per 100,000 across the 51 states under investigation. The average poverty rate is approximately 13%, with a variability of approximately 3%. The average unemployment rate is approximately 4%, with a variability of approximately 1%. Residents with a bachelor’s degree or higher have an average education attainment of approximately 35%, with a variance of approximately 7%. The average economic stability, measured by GDP across the 51 states, was approximately US \$533,556 million. Finally, the average mental health risk across the 51 states is approximately 44 risks per 100,000 of the state population.

Next to. Table 3 demonstrates that certain factors, such as unemployment, education attainment of residents with bachelor’s degrees or higher, and mental health risk, have a positive and significant impact on the opioid crisis in the United States. Conversely, economic stability has a negative and significant influence on the opioid crisis, indicating that an increase in unemployment, education attainment of residents with bachelor’s degrees or higher, and mental health risk will contribute to a greater opioid crisis, whereas an increase in economic stability will decrease the opioid crisis. This outcome aligns with the findings of Adejumo (2024), who discovered that an increase in economic growth reduced the opioid addiction crisis in the United States. Furthermore, it corroborates Zhang’s (2023) research, which showed that the opioid epidemic has intensified the deterioration of mental health. The model’s overall probability value of 0.007 suggests that the fitted OLS regression is statistically significant.

This indicates a significant association between the opioid crisis and social determinants, such as poverty, unemployment, education attainment of residents with a bachelor's degree or higher, economic stability, and mental health risk.

Table 5 presents the significance of the independent variables and their respective contributions estimated by the ANN model. It is evident that the educational attainment of residents with a bachelor's degree or higher has made the greatest contribution of 100% to the opioid crisis. Next in line are unemployment, economic stability, poverty, and mental health risk, each contributing 89.7%, 75.2%, 37%, and 23.5%, respectively. The estimated artificial neural network (ANN) achieved 70.6% accuracy with a minimally insignificant error rate of 0.001. This regression model outperforms the standard ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model in terms of prediction and extends the findings of Che et al. (2017) and Ellis et al. (2019).

Conclusion and policy implications

Recent studies on the socioeconomic indices of the opioid crisis in developed economies, such as the United States, have not included mental health as a social determinant of the opioid crisis, resulting in a significant gap that requires bridging. Therefore, to close the gap left by earlier research, this study incorporates mental health and economic stability into the social determinants of the opioid crisis in the United States using OLS regression and a machine learning model.

Meanwhile, the inclusion of mental health risk in the social determinants indicates that an increase in mental health risk exacerbates the opioid crisis, whereas an increase in economic stability leads to a reduction in the opioid crisis in the 51 states under review. This, however, suggests the need to adopt a sustainable policy that mitigates mental health risk and enhances economic stability to effectively address the opioid crisis. At the individual and community levels, it is necessary to improve the material and social environment for those at risk of, struggling with, or recovering from the opioid crisis. Interventions may include interventions across the continuum of care: prevention, harm reduction, treatment, and recovery.

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